

Supporting Information

Light-powered liquid crystal network polymer actuator using TiO₂ nanoparticle as an inorganic UV-light absorber

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Figure. S1: UV-vis absorption spectrum: a) TiO₂, b) Tinuvin460.

Figure. S2: EDX-map from the dispersion of Ti in the number of polymerized films: a) LCN/C-V, b) LCN/C-VI, c) LCN/C-VII.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

Figure. S3: AFM images of planar (images on the left) and homeotropic (images on the right) oriented surfaces: a) LCN/C-I, b) LCN/C-II, c) LCN/C-III, d) LCN/C-IV, e) LCN/C-V, f) LCN/C-VI, g) LCN/C-VII.

Figure. S4. Self-oscillation patterns during irradiation with polarized light: a) LCN/C-I, b) LCN/C-II, c) LCN/C-III, d) LCN/C-IV, e) LCN/C-V, f) LCN/C-VI, g) LCN/C-VII, h) LCN/C-VIII.

